

Participant Information Sheet - Children aged 6-9 years V5

The COVID-19 virus has changed all of our lives. Schools have closed lots of people are having to work from home and not go out. Others are not able to work. This is all to try to stop the virus from spreading and making people ill.

We are inviting you to take part in a research study so that we can learn more about this virus. This will help scientists to work out how we can stop the virus from doing so much harm. Please read this information, discuss it with an adult, and then decide if you want to take part.

What is the study about?

This research study is about the new coronavirus- COVID-19. COVID is new, so there are some things we know but lots of things we don't know.

WHAT DO WE ALREADY KNOW ABOUT COVID-19	WHAT DON'T WE KNOW AND HOPE VIRUS WATCH WILL FIND OUT
✓ We know that grown-ups often get a cough and a high temperature when they get COVID.	✗ We don't know whether children have different symptoms like tummy ache, diarrhoea or feeling sick.
✓ We know that COVID has made some adults very ill but that children are extremely unlikely to get very ill with COVID.	✗ We don't know how many people just get a mild illness a bit like a cold or if children can catch COVID without getting ill at all.
✓ We know that our bodies remember some infections so they can fight them off in future.	✗ We don't know if getting COVID once will stop you from getting it again.
✓ We know that COVID can spread very easily.	✗ We don't know how often children spread COVID.

If you have any queries, please contact the UCL Virus Watch Project Manager: viruswatch@ucl.ac.uk
1-19 Torrington Place, Fitzrovia, London WC1E 7HB

<p>✓ We know the government has given us lots of advice to stop COVID from spreading.</p>	<p>✗ We don't know how much people are able to follow this advice.</p>
---	--

Why do you want me to take part?

The Virus Watch study needs everybody in each household to take part so it is very important that we include children and young people as well as grown-ups.

We need to know how many children and young people get COVID and whether they spread it to others in the house. This means we would like everyone in your household to take part.

This will help us understand how useful it is to close schools, how long they need to close for and when this should happen.

Do I have to take part?

No. It is up to you to decide whether to take part or not. You can leave the study at any time and you don't have to give us a reason.

What will I need to do?

The study has several parts; these are:

- 1) online reporting of illnesses and other information
- 2) looking at medical records from hospitals
- 3) a swabbing study to tell if people have caught COVID
- 4) a blood test study to tell if people have developed immunity to COVID.

We want all households who are part of Virus Watch to take part in the first two parts but only some of the households will be selected to take part in the third and fourth studies. We will choose which households to invite into the swabbing and blood test studies later so that we get a good mix of households that can best tell us about how COVID is affecting groups of people.

1) At the start of the study, an adult in your household will answer some questions about you. We want to know how old you are and whether you have any medical conditions like asthma.

Online illness reporting study - Whenever anyone in your house is sick with coughs and colds and other signs that could be COVID they will need to write down how they are feeling every day that they are ill. Your family can help you with this. Each week an adult in your house will get an e-mail asking them to say whether or not anyone was ill and to record their symptoms on a computer survey.

We would like to **look at your medical records** to record any doctor or hospital visits related to respiratory infections that you may have made. We may do this for up to 5 years. If you have any queries, please contact the UCL Virus Watch Project Manager: viruswatch@ucl.ac.uk
1-19 Torrington Place, Fitzrovia, London WC1E 7HB

years after the end of the study. This is because we expect this virus to come back each winter.

3) Some, but not all households will also be asked to provide **nose and throat swabs** during illness. This does not hurt and involves a parent or guardian taking a tiny brush and gently brushing the back of your throat, then brushing the inside of your nose. This is then sent to scientists in a laboratory that will test it for COVID-19 and store it to test for other common respiratory infections (like colds and flu).

We **may** also ask you to take more nose and throat swabs on different days when someone else in your house has been ill. This will tell us how quickly and easily COVID-19 spreads from person to person and how often people get COVID without getting ill.

4) We **may** also ask you to give a small amount of blood on two separate occasions (About 2 tablespoons full - 30ml). We can use a numbing cream so you don't feel the sting of the needle as much. This blood sample will tell us important things about how our body's immune system responds to COVID-19 and other respiratory infections and how long this protection might last.

If you do not wish to provide a blood sample, we **may** ask you to provide a finger prick sample instead. This is done by making a small prick into your finger and collecting a few drops of blood into a small tube.

5) We **may** also ask you to provide finger prick samples like that described above if someone in your household has COVID-19, on day 2 of their illness and one and two months later.

You don't have to give blood it is completely up to you to decide and you can still take part in the study if you choose not to give blood.

How long will this study go for?

This study will run until spring next year (2021).

What if I have more questions?

If you have any more questions you can ask an adult to send us an email to: viruswatch@ucl.ac.uk

Thank you for reading about Virus Watch

If you have any queries, please contact the UCL Virus Watch Project Manager: viruswatch@ucl.ac.uk
1-19 Torrington Place, Fitzrovia, London WC1E 7HB